

Big Data Visualisation in the Maritime Industry

Luis Lourenço

UNINOVA—Centre of Technology and
Systems (CTS)
FCT Campus
Caparica, Portugal
lcl@uninova.pt

Paulo Figueiras

UNINOVA—Centre of Technology and
Systems (CTS)
FCT Campus
Caparica, Portugal
paf@uninova.pt

Amin Khodamoradi

UNINOVA—Centre of Technology and
Systems (CTS)
FCT Campus
Caparica, Portugal
a.khodamoradi@uninova.pt

André Grilo

UNINOVA—Centre of Technology and
Systems (CTS)
FCT Campus
Caparica, Portugal
a.grilo@uninova.pt

Bruno Rêga

UNINOVA—Centre of Technology and
Systems (CTS)
FCT Campus
Caparica, Portugal
b.rega@uninova.pt

Ruben Costa

UNINOVA—Centre of Technology and
Systems (CTS)
FCT Campus
Caparica, Portugal
rddc@uninova.pt

Ricardo Jardim-Gonçalves

UNINOVA—Centre of Technology and
Systems (CTS)
FCT Campus
Caparica, Portugal
rg@uninova.pt

Abstract—VesselAI aims to develop, validate and demonstrate a unique framework to unlock the potential of extreme-scale data and advanced HPC, AI and Digital Twin technologies in the maritime industry. With the growth of data and the digitalization of the sector comes the need to process and visualise this information as the maritime industry generates and consumes huge amounts of different types of data every day. This paper presents literature review focusing on two aspects: (1) an examination of visualization tools available, and (2) an investigation into existing works and studies within the domain of Big Data visualization. This study addresses specific visualization requirements pertinent to the Maritime domain, including the necessity for intricate spatial-temporal visualizations encompassing diverse datasets such as weather patterns, vessel trajectories, and Automatic Identification System (AIS) data. VesselAI intends to build the VesselAI Visualisation and Reporting Engine to empower maritime users and stakeholders to make informed decisions and gather knowledge from data. To this end a platform based on Apache Superset was applied and tested in response to challenges faced by maritime stakeholders and the findings indicate that Apache Superset's robust capabilities, including a vast number of visualisation types supported, out-of-the-box data connectors, customization options, and security features, effectively met the requirements identified in the literature and by pilot users.

Keywords— Data Visualisation, Maritime Industry, Big Data, AIS, Superset.

I. INTRODUCTION

The explosive growth of Big Data in the maritime industry presents both challenges and opportunities. With increasing amounts of data being generated each second, it is crucial to have effective tools for processing and visualising this information in a way that enables stakeholders to quickly turn data into knowledge. Data visualisation is the graphical

representation of information and data. By using visual elements, such as charts, graphs, and maps, data visualisation tools provide an accessible way to see and understand trends, outliers, and patterns in data. The European research project VesselAI aims to capitalize on this growth of data by developing, validating and demonstrating a unique framework to unlock the potential of extreme-scale data and advanced High-Performance Computing (HPC), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Digital Twin technologies, and hence to promote the adoption and application of Big Data-driven innovations and solutions for the Maritime industry. Within the project there is a need to visualise and interpret different types of data, from ship sensors, simulation parameters, weather data or algorithms' results. The project intended to build and deploy a data visualisation solution for the Maritime domain with Big Data capabilities, the VesselAI Visualisation and Reporting Engine, enabling users to easily create multi-purpose dashboards for the Maritime Domain.

This paper presents a comprehensive literature review focusing on two vital aspects related to Big Data visualisation: (1) an exploration of the diverse range of available visualisation tools designed to handle large and complex datasets, and (2) an investigation into similar works and studies in the domain of Big Data visualisation. Additionally, this work seeks to address specific Maritime domain's visualisation requirements such as the need for complex spatial-temporal visualisations of different datasets like weather, vessel trajectories or Automatic Identification System (AIS) and to choose and adapt a state-of-the-art visualisation solution for the Maritime industry.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, the rapid growth of Big Data has revolutionized various industries, opening new frontiers for data-driven decision-making and analysis. In this era of

information abundance, data visualisation has emerged as a crucial tool for transforming complex datasets into insightful and actionable visual representations. This section presents a literature review of two key aspects related to Big Data visualisation: (A) available tools for visualising large and complex datasets and (B) similar works and studies in the domain of Big Data visualisation.

A. Available Tools for Big Data Visualisation

In this section, a selection of prominent data visualisation tools that have been designed to handle Big Data are presented.

We began by conducting a literature review using databases such as Google Scholar and IEEE Xplore with Keywords such as "big data visualization tools," "big data visualization" and "data visualization" guided our search. Key articles and reviews provided initial insights into the most recognized tools.

Each tool is evaluated based on its features, capabilities, scalability, ease of use, security features, and compatibility with different data sources. The discussion includes both commercial and open-source solutions to provide a holistic view of the current landscape of Big Data visualisation tools. By understanding the strengths and limitations of each tool, researchers and practitioners can make informed decisions when choosing the most suitable tool for their specific requirements.

- Tableau [1]: Tableau is a widely used data visualisation tool that enables users to create interactive and shareable dashboards. It has a user-friendly interface and can handle large datasets effectively.
- Power BI [2]: Microsoft Power BI is another popular data visualisation tool that allows users to create insightful dashboards and reports. It integrates well with other Microsoft products and services.
- D3.js [3]: D3.js is a powerful JavaScript library that provides a wide range of data visualisation options. It allows for greater customization and flexibility but might require more coding expertise.
- Apache Superset [4]: Superset is an open-source data exploration and visualisation platform developed by Airbnb. It supports various data sources and offers a wide range of chart types.
- QlikView and Qlik Sense [5]: QlikView and Qlik Sense are data visualisation and business intelligence tools that offer powerful data discovery and interactive visualisations.
- Google Looker Studio [6]: Google Looker Studio is a free tool by Google that enables users to create interactive reports and dashboards using various data sources.
- Plotly [7]: Plotly is a Python graphing library that provides interactive, web-based visualisations, and is suitable for Big Data analysis.
- Apache Zeppelin [8]: Apache Zeppelin is an open-source web-based notebook that supports data exploration, visualisation, and collaboration.

- ggplot2 [9]: ggplot2 is an R library that offers an extensive grammar of graphics for data visualisation.
- Matplotlib [10]: Matplotlib is a Python library to create static, 2D visualisations and is often used for Big Data analysis.

TABLE I. TOOLS FOR BIG DATA VISUALISATION

Tools	Features				
	Standalone	Ease of use	Open-Source	Customisable	Security Features
Tableau	Yes	++	No	No	Yes
Power BI	Yes	++	No	No	Yes
D3.js	No	--	Yes	Yes	Depends on implementation
Apache Superset	Yes	++	Yes	Yes	Yes
Qlik Sense	Yes	++	No	No	Yes
Google Looker Studio	Yes	+	No	No	Yes
Plotly	No	-	Yes	Yes	Depends on implementation
Apache Zeppelin	Yes	-	Yes	Yes	Yes
ggplot2	No	-	Yes	Yes	Depends on implementation
Matplotlib	No	-	No	Yes	Depends on implementation

The comparison of various data visualization tools reveals distinct characteristics essential for big data visualization. Standalone solutions such as Tableau, Google Looker Studio, Power BI and Qlik Sense offer ease of use and multiple features and data connections but lack open-source flexibility and customizability. Apache Zeppelin and Superset also offer the same features with open-source code and customizability although Apache Zeppelin is not so easy to use for the average users as the other solutions in the standalone category. Conversely, programming options like D3.js, Plotly, ggplot2, and Matplotlib provide extensive customization but often require higher expertise for utilization.

B. Similar Works and Studies in Big Data Visualisation

This section delves into the existing literature and research papers related to Big Data visualisation. Various case studies and academic publications that showcase the successful application of data visualisation techniques to gain insights from data are presented. By reviewing these works, the aim is to identify common trends, best practices, and challenges encountered in Big Data visualisation projects. Additionally, this work highlights the methodologies and approaches used in these studies to inspire and guide future researchers in their data visualisation endeavours.

The authors of [11] discuss the future research challenges and emerging applications in Big Data visualisation and analytics, highlighting the importance of effectively visualising

and analysing large datasets to gain valuable insights. They point out that there is a need for innovative visualisation techniques and tools to handle the increasing complexity and scale of Big Data. The article also emphasizes the potential impact and benefits of Big Data visualisation and analytics in various domains.

The survey [12] presents an extensive review of multiple solutions for large data visualisation providing a detailed comparison of the main functional and non-functional characteristics of the surveyed tools. The authors also highlight that big data visualization tools have evolved as part of larger Data Management Systems (DMS), or as standalone software or plugins specifically designed for data visualization tasks.

The authors of [13] surveyed ways of making data visualisation more efficient and effective and after an intense review of techniques and tools of data visualisation presented 3 techniques to make data visualisation more effective: (1) Visualisation specifications - the method by which users can articulate their visualisation preferences and requirements; (2) Efficient approaches for data visualisation - the data is processed according to specified visualisation requirements to generate efficient and scalable visualisations, prioritizing interactive speed; (3) Data visualisation recommendation - to auto-complete an incomplete specification, or to discover more interesting visualisations based on a reference visualisation.

In [14] the authors survey the main challenges and big data visualisation tools. They concluded that interactivity of visualization is of utmost importance and good visualisation tools should produce interactive visualisations. From the analysis of the different tools, they conclude that there is not a clear choice between them and that users choose the best for their specific requirements.

The authors of [15] provide a study of various chart types available for data visualisation and analyse rules for employing each one of them, they also examined some of the most promising visualisation tools available. They conclude visualisation techniques can boost the decision-making process by enabling human cognition and perception within various IoT domains. The authors of [16] present the limitations of traditional visualisation systems in the Big Data era. Additionally, they discuss the major prerequisites and challenges like real-time interaction, on-the-fly visualisation, visual scalability, user assistance and personalization that should be addressed by modern visualisation systems.

The authors of [17] address the importance of data visualisation, and its role in the effective communication and interpretation of data in various sectors. Concrete examples of the application of data visualisation in business management, scientific research, journalism, media, politics, and government management are provided and it highlights the usefulness in each of these contexts. In addition, they review various tools and software that are widely used for data visualisation. In [18], the authors provided a literature review of data visualisation and Business Intelligence tools to proceed with the creation of a business intelligence platform and found that Apache Superset is the best platform for the creation of their solution.

The authors of [19] present a use case study that follows the Italian project Data Analytics Framework (DAF) starting from selection of the datasets to the creation phase of dashboards, using Apache Superset as the main dashboarding tool. It highlights the ability of this national platform to transform the analysis of a large amount of data into simple visual representations with a clear and effective language. The authors [20] reviewed different Big Data visualisation approaches and presented examples of GIS-based dashboards designed in Apache Superset. The dashboards represented relationship between air quality and traffic density with different visualisation methods and they concluded that dashboards are very useful tools to focus on the data produced from smart city implementations and to understand data with dynamic representations.

The authors of [21] present a use case where they develop a solution to analyse and visualise data of electricity usage, to this end they utilize multiple technologies from Apache Spark for data processing, Apache Kafka for streaming data and Apache superset for data visualisation. Their open-source approach using Apache technologies easily imported both batch and streaming data and was able to display that information in superset, however they failed to reach second-level response in the visualisations due to constrained by HBase Scan performance.

The authors of [22] present a Complex Event Processing (CEP) engine for detecting anomalies in real time and demonstrate it using a series of real monitoring data from the geological carbon sequestration domain. To visualise data Superset was selected due to its highly customizable dashboards. They showed that the microservice-oriented, distributed architecture plays a crucial role in expanding the capacity of computing systems to handle variations in structure and employing highly interactive and user-friendly web interfaces in the development of intelligent monitoring systems (IMS) is very important because these interfaces enable non-programmer domain users to stay involved and easily access the information and knowledge generated by CEP.

The authors of [23] provided a review of maritime traffic data visualisation techniques. The data visualisation techniques in the fields of spatiotemporal vessel trajectories and vessel traffic density have been comprehensively surveyed. They concluded that there is an opportunity to adopt these techniques to understand maritime traffic data and improve maritime transportation safety in practical applications.

The authors of [24] elaborate on how to create meaningful data visualisations for decision support with focus on maritime applications, they provide a review on visualisation, the importance of dashboards, and the importance of spatial-temporal data visualisation in the maritime domain. The authors of [25] demonstrate the use of visual analytics techniques to analyse Automatic Identification System (AIS) data by showing how visual analytics approaches can help in exploring properties of the data, detecting problems, and finding ways to clean and improve the data. They also describe two analysis scenarios focusing on the events of vessel stopping and on the vessel traffic through the strait between the bay of Brest, France, and the outer sea.

Finally, the authors of [26] aim to analyse climate change data using two Big Data processing frameworks. By using these tools, they were able to perform complex queries and analysis on large datasets with ease. Superset was used to create interactive dashboards that display the results of the analysis. The dashboards help users to explore the data and gain insights into climate change trends.

III. RESEARCH APPROACH

To address the challenges faced by the Maritime industry, a comprehensive study was conducted, including the gathering of requirements from maritime stakeholders and conducting a literature review of existing data visualisation tools and spatiotemporal data visualisation techniques. This enabled the identification of the key challenges and opportunities in the field and guided the creation of the VesselAI platform's Visualisation and Reporting Engine. Some of the requirements are the following:

- Spatiotemporal data visualisation – This type of visualisation is key to multiple use cases within the Maritime Domain (e.g., displaying multiple vessel positions in a map in real time).
- Batch and streaming data capabilities – Some use cases require data processing and visualisation in near-real time while others require processing and visualisation of historical data or a combination of both.
- Easy to use – The tool needs to be used by multiple types of users with different types of expertise. The creation of simple dashboards should be possible for all users.
- Connection to multiple sources – Data needs to be gathered from multiple different sources (e.g., Excel and CSV files, databases, message brokers, etc.).
- User roles – For some use cases different user types with different levels of access need to utilize the solution.
- Security – Due to the importance and privacy of data the solution needs to guarantee the security of data.

Some challenges regarding the data in the Maritime Domain relate to the challenges of Big Data. Those challenges and the strategies employed to address them are the following:

- Variety - Maritime applications require many different types of data (AIS data, ship sensors, weather data, etc.) – Creation of visualisations tailored to each type of data modular components to enhance customization to each scenario.
- Velocity - Maritime applications require visualisations in real-time with real-time data - Enable the visualisation of streaming data in real-time by connecting the visualisations to data through message brokers like Apache Kafka.
- Veracity - Applications that use huge amounts of data require the ability to deal with errors in data. - This

challenge will be solved before the visualisation layer with data cleansing operations although The SQL Integrated Development Environment (IDE) also provide some data cleansing capabilities.

- Volume - Maritime applications use extremely large volumes of data - Aggregate, summarize and/or compress data to provide responsive visualisations.

IV. FINDINGS

The VesselAI Visualisation and Reporting Engine is based on a custom instance of Apache Superset. The customization includes the look and feel change to match the rest of the VesselAI tools, the support for Mapbox and the inclusion and configuration of the connection with Apache Druid to allow for an easy integration of streaming data. The customization also included some specific visualisation types that were developed for the project. Some template dashboards for some specific maritime use-cases were created and included to speed up the process of new dashboards by the maritime users.

Apache Superset was chosen because it was designed to handle Big Data, for its out-of-the-box data connectors and its capability of customization. The open-source factor is also important because it allows more flexibility for the development and implementation. The security and user role management capabilities included in Superset are also important. Superset responds to all the requirements presented in the literature and by the pilot users. The main characteristics of the VesselAI Visualisation and Reporting Engine are:

- An intuitive interface for visualising datasets and crafting interactive dashboards.
- Code-free visualisation builder to extract and present datasets.
- A SQL IDE for preparing data for visualisation, including a rich metadata browser.
- A lightweight semantic layer which empowers data analysts to quickly define custom dimensions and metrics.
- An extensible security model that allows configuration of very intricate rules on who can access which product features and datasets.
- The ability to add custom visualisation plugins.
- A cloud-native architecture designed from the ground up for scale.
- Integration with major authentication backends (database, OpenID, LDAP, OAuth, REMOTE_USER, etc.)
- Multiple visualisations for time-series data and support for Mapbox.

The design of Superset revolves around four main components:

- The Data component, which is responsible for connecting Superset to data sources and retrieving and selecting data sets present in such data sources.

- The Charts component, which enables the definition of custom visualisation methods from the data sets selected in the Data component.
- The Dashboards component, which is responsible for the aggregation of the visualisation methods defined in the Charts component into custom dashboards.
- The SQL Lab component, which allows for the creation of custom and complex SQL rules to fine-tune the data retrieved from data sources and selected from data sets, enabling data aggregation, fusion and cleaning.

The Data component enables users to connect to an array of data sources, from databases to message queues. Further, other data sources may be used by adding new database drivers to the Superset instance. Moreover, other types of data sources may be connected to Superset, such as JSON, CSV and Excel files or SQL query engines, such as Apache Druid or Presto. Further, Superset also allows users to save and load saved queries, created through the SQL Lab component, as well as revisit their query history.

Another requirement of the project was that the visualisation platform would need to be able to display data coming in streams. To that end Apache Druid was deployed alongside Superset to receive data coming from multiple message brokers like Apache Kafka or RabbitMQ and display the data in Superset in a way that is indistinguishable for the user. The user can connect to Druid and get data from these sources in the same way as any other database or source file.

Given the nature of the data of the Maritime Domain the capability to display spatiotemporal data visualisations based on maps and positions around the world is crucial. In this field Superset provides multiple chart types that cater to this need which are visible in Figure 1 and the integration with Mapbox [27] is simple, enhancing spatiotemporal and geospatial data visualisation capabilities and offering extensive mapping services with high customization options.

Fig. 1- Map charts options.

In Fig.1 the integration with Mapbox and the different support for map-based visualisations is displayed.

Figs. 2-6 present examples of visualisations made for the VesselAI project. These visualisations focus on showcasing the positions and movements of ships on a map. The aim is to present this information in a simple and intuitive way, so that the viewer can quickly and easily understand the information being presented. The visualisations could take various forms, such as a map with markers indicating the locations of ships, or a graph showing the movement of ships over time. The important aspect is that the visualisations should effectively communicate the positions and movements of ships in a manner that is easy to comprehend. All the visualisations are interactive (e.g., the user can zoom in and out, select subsets of data based on filters, etc.).

Such interaction capabilities are crucial due to the Big Data nature of the requirements, for example, the capability to filter the datasets for a given time period or to filter for some specific vessel or group of vessels is very important to the use cases faced by the maritime users and allow them to quickly get the information that they need without complex queries or having to rely on multiple different visualisations for the same dataset. The results of the analysis by the users can be downloaded as JSON or CSV files or even the visualisations themselves can be downloaded as images.

Fig. 2- Ship Groups

Fig. 6- Routes and weather

Fig. 2 present visualizations based on the grouping of large numbers of vessels within a given area based on the Brest AIS dataset, this visualisation is more focus in the big picture and groups of vessels rather than a single vessel. Fig. 3 there is a different way of grouping vessel and a visualisation of the different routes taken by each vessel within the area.

A practical example is the visualisation of prediction models' results: A model was trained to predict the available mooring zones available in a desired port for the estimated arrival time of a given vessel. The results of this model are stored in a database or sent to a message queue connected to the visualisation platform and, in this way, the results can be shown in real-time in an intuitive manner. Within VesselAI the platform was often used to present the results of the different AI models developed within the project. The mooring zones model output is shown in Fig. 4.

Another prime example of the visualisations used in this project is Fig. 5 where the input parameters, the output results and the desired (true) values of a route prediction model are presented simultaneously for comparison by the user. The flexibility provided by Superset is very important in use cases like these where both the final users and the developers of the models can use and create different dashboards and visualisations from the same data for their different needs, developers can use it to track the improvements on their models and end users can get the results without having to analyse complex files or go to different platforms.

In Fig. 6 the capacity to show multiple different types of data at the same time is evident with a dashboard that intends to show a given route of a Vessel and the available weather data, wind speed, wave weight and height for the area surrounding the vessel path. This example demonstrates the ability of displaying different sources of data in the same visualisation and a dashboard with different data sources that enhance each other and allow for better decision-making.

The visualisations presented show diverse use cases with different types of requirements, different types of data for different types of users all within the same platform.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A. Limitations

While this study provides a comprehensive comparison of several big-data visualization tools, there are some limitations:

Exclusion of Emerging Tools: This study primarily focuses on well-known and widely used big-data visualization tools. As a result, emerging tools that are still not featured in research papers are not included.

Limited Performance Testing: Due to resource constraints, extensive performance testing with large datasets was not conducted for each tool to truly test the "Big Data" capabilities of all tools.

B. Concluding Remarks

The results of the presented study showed that Apache Superset was a suitable tool for the visualisation requirements and challenges of the VesselAI platform. The findings indicate that Apache Superset was able to provide the required visualisation capabilities and data source connections for handling Big Spatiotemporal Data in the maritime domain, effectively addressing the challenges identified in the literature review and meeting the requirements gathered from stakeholders. The SQL lab and data components of Apache Superset revealed very useful for data integration and facilitated the construction of visualisations even when working with different data sources and different types of users were able to construct visualisations for their own needs.

Furthermore, the results demonstrated that the integration of Apache Superset and Apache Druid enables the VesselAI Visualisation and Reporting Engine to effectively support both batch and streaming data visualisations and dashboards. This includes the ability to read and display data from message brokers such as Apache Kafka, providing a complete solution

for visualising Big Spatiotemporal Data in the maritime industry.

In conclusion, the presented research has demonstrated the capability of the VesselAI Visualisation and Reporting Engine, based on Apache Superset, to effectively visualise Big Data in the maritime industry. The platform meets the requirements gathered from maritime stakeholders and provides the ability to create customized dashboards.

C. Future Work

As future work, the plan is to extend the platform by creating standard dashboards with specific designs for common datasets in the maritime industry, such as AIS data and weather data. This will further enhance the platform's ability to turn data into actionable insights and help stakeholders in the maritime industry make informed decisions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the European Commission for the support and funding under the scope of Horizon 2020 VesselAI Project (Grant Agreement Number 957237) and the partners of the VesselAI Project Consortium and under the scope of Horizon 2.4 AI-DAPT Project (Grant Agreement Number 101135826).

References

- [1] Salesforce, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tableau.com/>.
- [2] Microsoft, "Power BI," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://powerbi.microsoft.com/>.
- [3] J. Heer, M. Bostock and V. Ogievetskiy, "D3.js," 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://d3js.org/>.
- [4] The Apache Software Foundation, "Apache Superset," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://superset.apache.org/>.
- [5] Qlik, "Qlik Sense," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.qlik.com/us/products/qlik-sense>.
- [6] Google, "Google Looker Studio," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://lookerstudio.google.com/navigation/reporting>.
- [7] Plotly, "Plotly," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://plotly.com/>.
- [8] Apache Software Foundation, "Apache Zeppelin," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://zeppelin.apache.org/>.
- [9] H. Wickham and W. Chang, "ggplot2," 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org/>.
- [10] J. Hunter, "Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment," *Computing in Science & Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 90--95, 2007.
- [11] G. Andrienko, N. Andrienko, S. Drucker, J.-D. Fekete, D. Fisher, S. Idreos, T. Kraska, K.-L. Ma and J. Mackinlay, "Big Data Visualization and Analytics: Future Research," *BigVis 2020: Big data visual exploration and analytics*, 2020.
- [12] E. Caldarola and A. Rinaldi, "Big Data Visualization Tools: A Survey," in *6th International Conference on Data Science, Technology and Applications*, 2017.
- [13] X. Qin, Y. Luo, N. Tang and G. Li, "Making data visualization more efficient and effective: a survey," *The VLDB Journal*, vol. 1, no. 29, pp. 93--117, 2020.
- [14] S. M. Ali, N. Gupta, G. K. Nayak and R. K. Lenka, "Big Data Visualization: Tools and Challenges," in *2016 2nd International Conference on Contemporary Computing and Informatics (IC3I)*, Greater Noida, India, 2016.
- [15] A. Protopsaltis, P. Sarigiannidis, D. Margounakis and A. Lytos, "Data Visualization in Internet of Things: Tools, Methodologies, and," in *Proceedings of the 15th international conference on availability, reliability and security*, 2020.
- [16] N. Bikakis, "Big Data Visualization Tools," *Encyclopedia of Big Data Technologies*, vol. abs/1801.08336, 2022.
- [17] C. Inastrilla, "Data Visualization in the Information Society," in *Seminars in Medical Writing and Education*, 2023, pp. 25--25.
- [18] G. Soares and M. Brito, "Business Intelligence Over and Above Apache Superset," in *18th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI)*, Aveiro, Portugal, 2023.
- [19] P. Michele, F. Fallucchi and E. De Luca, "Create dashboards and data story with the data & analytics frameworks," in *Research Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research*, Springer, 2019, pp. 272--283.
- [20] R. Bokvir and A. C. Aydinoglu, "Big urban data visualization approaches within the smart city: GIS-Based Open-Source dashboard example," *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, Vols. XLVI-4/W5-2021, pp. 125--130, 2021.
- [21] C. Yang, T. Chen, E. Kristiani and S. Wu, "The implementation of data storage and analytics platform for big data lake of electricity usage with spark," *The Journal of Supercomputing*, pp. 5934-5959, 2020.
- [22] A. Sun, Z. Zhong, H. Jeong and Q. Yang, "Building complex event processing capability for intelligent environmental monitoring," *Environmental Modelling & Software*, vol. 116, pp. 1--6, 2019.
- [23] K. Wang, M. Liang, Y. Li, J. Liu and R. W. Liu, "Maritime Traffic Data Visualization: A Brief Review," in *2019 IEEE 4th International Conference on Big Data Analytics (ICBDA)*, Suzhou, China, 2019.
- [24] M. Karlsson, S. Haraldson, M. Lind, E. Olsson, T. Andersen and M. Tichavska, "Data visualisation tools for enhanced situational awareness in maritime operations," in *Maritime Informatics*, Springer, 2020, pp. 355--372.

[25] N. Andrienko and G. Andrienko, “Visual Analytics of Vessel Movement,” in *Guide to Maritime Informatics*, Springer, 2021, p. 149–170.

[26] S. Greca, I. Shehi and J. Nuhi, “Analyzing climate changes impacts using big data Hadoop,” in *Recent*

Trends and Applications in Computer Science RTA-CSIT, Tirana, Albania, 2023.

[27] Mapbox, Inc., “Mapbox,” 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mapbox.com/>.